

On Adhesion Modeling and Control of a Vortex Actuator for Climbing Robots

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Abstract— In this article, the critical adhesion force and achievable payload of a Vortex Actuator (VA) are analyzed under 3-DOF surface rotations. A model-based control scheme is later proposed, with the goal of maintaining VA adhesion when immobilized, while limiting the power consumption and counteracting disturbances leading to Center-of-Mass (CoM) variations. Finally, the model-based control scheme is experimentally evaluated with the VA prototype on a flat surface under linear motions and rotations, thus supporting the incorporation of the VA in Climbing Robots (CRs) for inspection and maintenance of both stationary and moving surfaces.

Keywords—*Electric Ducted Fan, Vortex Actuation, Negative Pressure, Force Modeling, Adhesion Control*

I. INTRODUCTION

Climbing Robots (CRs) targeting inspection and maintenance tasks have been traditionally multidimensional in terms of utilized adhesion technologies and motion capabilities, which have been tailored to match specific application scenarios, surface materials and geometries [1]. Efficient and autonomous handling of tools and sensors for Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) and Repair (NDR) tasks requires high payload capabilities, resulting in high adhesion requirements that are achieved by powerful actuators [2]. In the case of Electric Ducted Fan (EDF)-enabled CRs, their important advantage of not requiring contact with the target surface alleviates the design challenges of adhesion in cases of curved, rough or non-ferromagnetic surfaces, but their high current draws creates the need for maximizing their adhesion performance while reducing their power consumption [3]–[5].

In EDF and generally rotor-based CR analyses found in related literature, the main research aspect focused on the negative pressure generation [6], generated thrust [3], [4], [7], experimental studies [8] or design approaches targeting the maximization of the adhesion performance [9], [10]. Recent work provided novel considerations and detailed presentation on the utilized hardware and software of the EDF-based CRs [11], [12], although no information was provided on adhesion modeling and control. Evaluation of these recent solutions was mostly performed on flat surfaces of constant orientation (e.g. wall, ceiling), while the reported force analyses was

constrained on that particular single-plane case [9]. In [13], force and torque models were provided for a rotor-based CR in the cases of both flat and curved surfaces, although no input was given on closed-loop force control or cabling effects.

To this goal, the authors proposed an EDF-based Vortex Actuation System (VAS), which provided a detailed analysis on various properties such as adhesion force, pressure distribution, current draw, motor temperature etc. during the VAS' operation when placed in variable distances from a surface [14]. The optimized EDF configuration was later installed in a CR design, which was evaluated on flat surfaces of variable inclinations via a PI-based scheme with setpoint force references [15]. While ensuring successful adhesion in all scenarios, the need for model-based control algorithms was highlighted, which would effectively reduce the overall consumption, as well as compensating for mechanical disturbances leading to Center-of-Mass (CoM) variations.

The novelty of this work is multiple. Firstly, the critical adhesion force required for maintaining adhesion in the case of a single static Vortex Actuator (VA) is investigated under 3-DOF surface rotations, while synthesized from both a geometrical analysis and dynamically-simulated numerical results. The second novelty stems from the incorporation of the extracted model in a control scheme for achieving adhesion while remaining immobilized, while limiting the power consumption and counteracting disturbances (e.g. moving cables) leading to Center-of-Mass (CoM) variations. Finally, the model-based control scheme is experimentally evaluated on the VA prototype under a moving and rotating flat surface, thus expanding the applicability of the proposed methodology from CRs on stationary surfaces to future CR solutions operating on moving structures (e.g. cranes, folding bridges).

The rest of this article is structured as follows. Section II presents the VAS and its main components, while Section III analyzes the adhesion modeling of the actuation unit from a geometrical and numerical approach. In Section IV, the adhesion control scheme is synthesized and presented in detail. The experimental evaluation of the proposed scheme on the VA prototype is presented in Section V. Finally, the concluding remarks are provided in Sections VI.

II. VORTEX ACTUATION SYSTEM

As presented in [14], the VAS was designed with the main goal of being easily adaptable for fitting EDFs of different

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dimensions and design characteristics. The prototype system was mainly designed for measuring the adhesion force F exerted from a test EDF to the test surface (Fig. 1). To achieve this, the EDF was mounted to a legged support structure where each of the four legs were connected to the baseplate via a load cell. In this configuration, the total measured force F is derived by the summation of the force measured by the four load cells.

Provided the general symmetry of the VAS structure, the flow distribution along circular sections around the EDF's longitudinal axis was assumed to be symmetrical, while the aerodynamic effect of the legged structure was assumed negligible. Among the different properties tested in the design methodology presented in [14], the distance of the test EDF from the test surface was conceptualized as variable and to this purpose the legged structure was equipped with multiple, inlets placed at predetermined intervals. In addition, customized shrouds of different outer radius were designed to be interchangeable via mounting brackets for evaluating the effect of the active surface and volume change on the attraction between the VAS and the test surface for a given distance.

Specifically, the VAS prototype presented in Fig. 1 and utilized for the experimental evaluation presented in Section V, incorporates an EDF with an inner duct diameter of 92 mm, overall weight 0.67 kg and a 12-blade fan, actuated via a brushless DC motor of 2350 W maximum power at 41000 maximum rpm, which provides a maximum free-flight thrust of 3.8 kg. A 3D-Printed customized shroud of 80 mm outer radius was implemented, following an outward curvature profile and constant shroud thickness 2 mm while set at the optimal distance of 15 mm from the test surface, as extracted from the methodology presented in [14].

The prototype uses the Turnigy AE-100A Electronic Speed Controller (ESC), while been powered by an external power supply. For measuring the force F_S generated from the EDF and acting on the test surface via the legged structure, four TE Connectivity FX1901 button-type load cells were utilized, while the force data was acquired via a Phidget Bridge. The overall VA enclosure was 3D printed from Polylactide (PLA), leading to an actuator unit with measured mass of approximately $m = 0.91$ kg. Finally, the control of the EDF's operation was achieved with an Arduino Mega and via a personal computer system running LabVIEW.

III. ADHESION MODELING

A. Geometrical Modeling

An important step towards minimization of the force needed for keeping the VA adhered and immobilized on a test surface, i.e. zero linear velocity $v = 0$, will be the modeling of the critical adhesion F_C . The force analysis of the extracted VA is presented in Fig. 2. While placed on the plane, defined by $\{x_0, y_0\}$ axes of the idle coordination system $G_0 = \{O, x_0, y_0, z_0\}$, the VA remains immobilized regardless of its adhesion force F_{VA} , given a plane reaction force equal to $F_{VA} + W$, where $W = mg$ defines the system's weight with m its mass and g the gravitational acceleration. Changing the VA orientation by angles $\{\varphi, \theta, \psi\} = \{\text{roll, pitch, yaw}\}$ around the $\{x, y, z\}$ axes, respectively, the system is momentarily placed on the derived plane $\{x_1, y_1\}$ defined by the new coordination system $G_1 = \{O, x_1, y_1, z_1\}$.

Fig. 1. The VAS prototype with highlighted components.

Fig. 2. VA force analysis while in (top) idle and (bottom) rotated state.

Rotations around an x - y - z sequence are performed via the following rotation matrix:

$$R_{\psi\theta\varphi} = \begin{bmatrix} c\psi c\theta & c\psi s\theta\varphi - c\varphi s\psi & s\varphi s\psi + c\varphi\psi s\theta \\ c\theta s\psi & c\varphi c\psi + s\varphi s\psi s\theta & c\varphi\psi s\theta - c\psi s\varphi \\ -s\theta & c\theta s\varphi & c\varphi c\theta \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

where $c\cdot$ and $s\cdot$ denote the trigonometric functions $\cos(\cdot)$ and $\sin(\cdot)$, respectively.

By defining $W_0 = [W_{x,0} \ W_{y,0} \ W_{z,0}]^T = [0 \ 0 \ -mg]^T$ as the weight vector in the idle coordination system G_0 , the resulting vector W_1 in G_1 will be:

$$W_1 = R_{\psi\theta\varphi} W_0 = \begin{bmatrix} -mg(s\varphi s\psi + c\varphi\psi s\theta) \\ mg(c\varphi c\psi + s\varphi s\psi s\theta) \\ -mgc\varphi c\theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} W_{x,1} \\ W_{y,1} \\ W_{z,1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

with the negative (-) sign denoting the direction of the weight vectors in relation to the positive definition of G (Fig. 2).

VA adhesion is characterized as successful when the system remains immobilized in all three axes. With $\sum F_{z_1} = 0$ and (2) giving the reaction force in the z direction $N = F_{VA} + mgc\varphi c\theta$, the resulting friction T will be defined as:

$$T = \mu N = \mu(F_{VA} + mgc\varphi c\theta), \quad (3)$$

where μ is the static friction constant. The force equilibrium in the $\{x_1, y_1\}$ plane equates the friction T with the vector addition of $W_{x,1}$ and $W_{y,1}$. Thus, by combining $\sum F_{\{x_1, y_1\}} = 0$ with (2) and (3) we receive the theoretical model describing the critical force $F_{VA} = F_C$ needed to achieve successful adhesion:

$$F_C = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } 0 \leq \gamma \leq \gamma_C \\ mg \left(\frac{\sqrt{(s\varphi)^2 + (c\varphi s\theta)^2}}{\mu - c\varphi c\theta} \right) & \text{for } \gamma_C \leq \gamma \leq (360^\circ - \gamma_C) \\ 0 & \text{for } (360^\circ - \gamma_C) \leq \gamma \leq 360^\circ \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

while constrained at the regions where the adhesion force becomes negative, which are defined by using the l^2 -norm (i.e. Euclidean norm) of the roll and pitch angles $\gamma = \sqrt{\varphi^2 + \theta^2}$ with value $\gamma_C = \varphi_C = \theta_C$ denoting the critical angle at which the VA unit begins operation for achieving adhesion.

Simulation of (4) for the physical properties of the VA prototype ($m = 0.91$ kg, $g = 9.80$ m/s², $\mu = 0.80$), leads to the three-dimensional representation displayed in Fig. 3. Such a geometrical representation will later play a fundamental role in the control of the VA, as it will provide a feedforward model outputting the reference forces needed to achieve successful adhesion regardless of surface orientation.

Considering that this analysis is performed for zero load attached on the VA ($m_L = 0$), the geometrical model (4) can provide an important estimation of the payload m_L than the VA can handle for a given critical force F_C :

$$m_L = \frac{F_C}{\left(\frac{\sqrt{(s\varphi)^2 + (c\varphi s\theta)^2}}{\mu - c\varphi c\theta} \right) g} - m_0 \quad (5)$$

where m_0 denotes the unloaded system's mass. Indicatively, by setting the maximum adhesion force of the VA prototype, which has been experimentally measured at approximately $F_{C,\max} = F_{VA,\max} = 80$ N, the simulation of (5) under the aforementioned physical quantities would return the maximum permitted payload m_L (Fig. 4). This analysis provides an important static map for achieving stable adhesion when placing a climbing robot under a specific orientation and for a given payload. As highlighted in Fig. 4, in the inverted case, highlighted for $\varphi = 180^\circ$ and $\theta = 0^\circ$, the VA's permitted payload reaches 7.24 kg, while in the most challenging case noted as $\varphi = 130^\circ$ and $\theta = 0^\circ$, the VA could manage approx. 4.18 kg. The maximum permitted payload is governed by the structural properties of the setup and is highlighted as $m_{L,\text{critical}}$.

Lastly, it must be noted that given the four force measurement points presented in Fig. 2 as $F_{S,i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, 4$, the total sensed force $F_S = \sum_{i=1}^4 F_{S,i}$ will be equal to the reaction force N . This provides a way to properly extract the applied adhesion force for different plane orientations via:

$$F_{VA} = F_S - mgc\varphi c\theta \quad (6)$$

Fig. 3. Critical force needed for successful adhesion of the VA unit on a surface of different roll and pitch inclinations.

Fig. 4. Maximum permitted payload for a single VA unit under different surface orientations.

B. Numerical Modeling

To numerically assess the adhesion performance of the VA, a simulation tool was utilized for generating accurate and real-life performances of the dynamic system. For the needs of generating dynamic responses of the VA in an accurate manner, MATLAB's Simscape was utilized. The capability for a direct parameterization of a dynamic model allowed it to be iteratively simulated following a parameters map that described the virtual equivalents of the system's real-world features and requirements. To this purpose, the Simscape's Multibody Contact Forces Library was used to simulate the physical quantities concerning the mechanical interactions between the robot's physical parts and its physical surroundings. A view of the simulation environment developed for the imported VA with the modified leg structure on a flat surface of variable 3-DOF rotations is presented in Fig. 5.

The dynamic simulations performed in Simscape Multibody included the VA initially touching the test surface under variable surface orientations, defined by roll φ and pitch θ angles. An exhaustive testing was performed for all angle combinations from 0° to 360° and adhesion forces ranging from

Fig. 5. Overview of MATLAB's Mechanics Explorer environment built for dynamically simulating the VA under different surface orientations.

Fig. 6. The error between the geometrical and the numerically extracted models for the critical adhesion force.

0 to 80 N. The criteria of the VA, remaining immobilized on the surface, produces the minimum adhesion force required for every roll and pitch combination, which acts as a numerical model representation $F_{C,N}(\varphi, \theta)$.

Indicatively, the extracted error $e_F = F_{C,N} - F_C$ between the dynamic simulations and the results provided by the geometrical model (4), is presented in Fig. 6 for both roll and pitch angles. This figure shows a near identical relationship of the two models, with a slight underestimation in the case of the static geometrical model and an error reaching a maximum of 0.25 N. Advantages of the numerical model extracted via Simscape are the incorporation of dynamic characteristics regarding the relative motions of the VA on the surface, while changes due to cable tension and other disturbances require the reacquisition of the model via a new simulation batch, thus rendering it problematic for use in online control structures.

IV. ADHESION CONTROL

The block diagram for the proposed adhesion control scheme is presented in Fig. 7. The critical adhesion F_c is calculated via (4) (denoted as G_1) in an online manner via the sensed orientation angles $\varphi, \theta \in [-\pi, \pi]$. Due to the cabling weight of the tethered VA, a constant percentage factor is tuned to assist the adhesion and counteract CoM disturbances during operation. The required force for achieving a successful

Fig. 7. Adhesion control block diagram.

adhesion F_{ref} is calculated as $F_{ref} = F_k + F_c$, where $F_k = K \cdot F_c$ with K being the disturbance compensator gain. The error e_F is computed as the difference of the current force F_{VA} and the reference value F_{ref} , which is fed to the controller C . The signal T denotes the throttle input signal sent for the VA and it is the control effort of C , required to achieve the intended force levels with a fast and smooth response. Finally, the force F_s measured from the load cells is properly translated to the adhesion force F_{VA} with the use of the equation (6) (noted as G_2 in Fig. 7) via the sensed orientation (φ, θ) of the setup.

For the tethered VA version and for attached payload, the variable gain K needs to be properly tuned in order to compensate for disturbances and model inaccuracies, while ensuring successful adhesion. To preliminarily evaluate this control scheme, a PI structure has been selected as controller C :

$$T(t) = K_p \left(e_F(t) + \frac{1}{T_I} \int_0^t e_F(t) dt \right), \quad (7)$$

where K_p is the proportional gain and T_I the reset time in minutes. As force-throttle nonlinearities have been documented in [14], this increases the difficulty in fine-tuning the control parameters K_p , and T_I for achieving efficient control performance throughout the EDFs operating range. For this reason, a gain scheduler is appropriately incorporated in the PI control structure, which adds the ability to alter the control parameters K_p and T_I according to the active region of operation, specified by the selected manipulated value:

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_p \\ T_I \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{p,m} \\ T_{I,m} \end{bmatrix} \text{ for } m=1, 2, \dots, M, \quad (8)$$

with $m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ denoting the active operating region and M the maximum number of regions.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Setup Components

To evaluate the control performance during dynamical changes on the orientation of the VA and, thus, the efficiency of the geometrical modeling, an experimental setup was implemented and is presented in Fig. 8. The VA is placed on a

Fig. 8. VAS setup with modified legged structure for evaluating the adhesion control performance on a test plate under variable orientations.

carbon fiber plate with the goal of maintaining the position of the VA without slippage or loss of adhesion, while the orientation of the system changed. The location and orientation of the test plate and the VA with respect to a global coordinate system were tracked via the VICON motion capture system providing a sub-millimeter accuracy. In Fig. 8, the tracked coordinate systems are denoted as $G_p = \{O_p, x_p, y_p, z_p\}$ and $G_{VA} = \{O_{VA}, x_{VA}, y_{VA}, z_{VA}\}$ for the plate and VA, respectively. This provided the ability of also measuring the linear velocities of the two objects, highlighted as v_p and v_{VA} , for evaluating their relative linear motions and identifying slippages.

The VA modified legged structure enabled the ability of force sensing while maintaining mobility. This enables experimentation with force control algorithms that assist the evaluation of the critical adhesion force modeling and the control performance on dynamic changes of the VA during operation. A rubber-type tire material was installed on the base of the loadcell sensors legs to replicate the same friction constant as the wheels of developed CR [15], which was statically measured as $\mu = 0.80$.

B. Adhesion Control Performance

During this preliminary experimental evaluation, the test plate was handheld and thus manually imposed disturbances were introduced for testing the compensation capabilities of the proposed control scheme (Fig. 9). The PI controller was finetuned with gain-scheduled parameters, while for the tuning of the constant parameter K , iterative experiments have been performed and has been set at a constant $K = 30\%$.

Fig. 10 presents the acquired results from the adhesion control experiment. In the examined case, the surface was manually subjected to 3-DOF rotations, highlighted by the plotting of φ_{VA} , θ_{VA} and ψ_{VA} angles, while the controller was generating reference forces F_{ref} via the combination of the geometrical model (4) and the parameter K . It can be also observed that the orientation change included the disturbances imposed by the manual handling of the setup which due to the tracked angle changes was also altering the F_{ref} .

In all examined test cases, the controller managed to maintain the VA adhesion and accurately regulate the force

Fig. 9. Photographic stills displaying the VA operation during manual rotations of the test surface.

based on the orientation of the surface, with an absolute mean error e_F of approximately 0.93 N. It also managed to keep the VA immobilized at all times, which was assessed via the tracked object linear velocities v_p and v_{VA} . No slippage was observed, with the surface velocity being tracked slightly larger than the one of the VA, with a relative mean absolute error of 0.02 m/s, which was a product of inertial characteristics, measurement inaccuracies and imposed vibrations.

As also shown in Fig. 10, the throttle signal did not exceed 35.5%, a value set only in the most challenging orientations. This effectively kept the power consumption at the low levels of mean 0.13 kW and maximum 0.35 W, in comparison to the maximal 2.35 kW that the selected EDF can consume. which highlights the potential for energy efficient responses.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The goal of this study was to investigate a single static Vortex Actuator (VA) from a adhesion modeling and control

Fig. 10. VA adhesion response F_{VAS} under alternating (φ, θ) plate orientation, along with the respective time responses of the reference force F_{ref} , control output throttle T , drawn power P and linear velocities of the plate v_{Plate} and VAS v_{VAS} .

point, while under 3-DOF surface rotational changes. The critical adhesion force and extracted achievable payload were modeled from both geometrical analysis and dynamically-simulated numerical results, which were characterized by a close match and minor force underestimation in the case of the geometrical model. The extracted model was incorporated in a PI-based control scheme for achieving VA adhesion while remaining immobilized. The experimental evaluation involved the VA on a manually handled surface and showed successful adhesion with absence of slippages, which proved the validity of the model-based adhesion method, while limiting the power consumption and counteracting for disturbances (e.g. moving cables, vibrations imposed by the EDF and manual handling) leading to performance degradations during operation.

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